

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
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In reply refer to:
08FBDT00-2017-F-0045

JUN 27 2017

Mr. Richard Bottoms
Chief, Regulatory Division
San Francisco District
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
1455 Market Street,
San Francisco, California 95825

Subject: Formal Consultation for the Goodyear Slough Morrow Lane Bridge Replacement Project, Suisun Marsh, Solano County, California (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' File number 2014-00103N)

Dear Mr. Bottoms:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) November 17, 2016, letter requesting informal consultation and subsequent January 12, 2017, electronic mail (e-mail) which modified the Corps' original determination and requested formal consultation with the U.S. Fish Wildlife Service (Service) for the Goodyear Slough Morrow Lane Bridge Replacement Project (project), Suisun Marsh, Solano County, California. In the January 12, 2017, e-mail, the Corps modified its original determination and determined that the proposed project may affect and is likely to adversely affect the endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*) (SMHM) and the endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) (CCR). The Corps retained the determinations from the November 17, 2016, letter that the proposed project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the threatened delta smelt (*Hypomesus transpacificus*) and its designated critical habitat, the endangered soft bird's-beak (*Chloropyron molle* ssp. *molle*) and its critical habitat, and the endangered Suisun thistle (*Cirsium hydrophilum* var. *hydrophilum*). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C 1531 *et seq.*)(Act).

Recent genetic analyses of rail species resulted in a change in the common name and taxonomy of the large, "clapper-type" rails (*Rallus longirostris*) of the west coast of North America to Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus*) (Maley and Brumfield 2013; Chesser *et al.* 2014). However, the change does not change the listing status of the species. The Service continues to recognize the species as the California clapper rail until the change in common name and taxonomy of the California clapper rail to Ridgway's rail is officially entered into the Federal Register.

In reviewing this project, the Service has relied upon: (1) the Corps' November, 17, 2016, letter requesting consultation; (2) the January 12, 2017, Corps e-mail modifying the Corps'

determination and request of formal consultation; (3) the September 2016 *Biological Assessment for NMFS- and USFWS-Managed Species Morrow Lane Bridge Replacement Project Solano County, California* (BA) prepared by AECOM; (4) telephone and e-mail communication between the Corps, AECOM and the Service; and (5) other information available to the Service.

Goodyear Slough is within the designated critical habitat for the delta smelt and contains in some part all of the Primary Constituent Elements (PCEs). The project will be utilizing pile removal and pile driving equipment in the aquatic environment that constitutes the delta smelt's designated critical habitat. The Service has reviewed the proposed project and its effects to the delta smelt's designated critical habitat. In designating critical habitat for the delta smelt, the Service identified the following PCEs essential to the conservation of the species:

PCE #1 is physical habitat for spawning. Spawning occurs primarily in the sloughs and shallow edges areas in the delta. Captive breeding has indicated sandy or gravel areas are preferred (Lindberg *et al.* 2003). The action area encompasses critical habitat that may be suitable for spawning and spawning activity is historically prevalent around the project area (California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) 2017). The project could disturb substrates that would increase turbidity; however, effects are considered temporary in nature and substrates are expected to return to pre-project conditions upon completion. The proposed actions are not expected to remove available spawning habitat substrates to a measurable degree. There is not expected to be a loss in habitat as the older bridge is proposed to be removed upon completion of the new bridge.

PCE #2 is suitable water quality for all life stages. The project does not discharge effluent or reduce the dilution properties of the available water through diversion. There is no anticipated reduction in the quality of available water from any of the proposed actions.

PCE #3 is river flow. The proposed project is not expected to diminish river flow, since the project is not expected to reduce or alter the flows of the Sacramento River or the San Joaquin River.

PCE #4 is salinity for rearing. The proposed project is not expected to have any effect on salinity, since the river flows will not be affected, thus not affecting the position of X2.

Based on the above analysis, the Service determines that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the delta smelt's critical habitat.

Soft bird's-beak has low potential to occur in the action area because the salt marsh habitat present is densely vegetated where tidally influenced and the remainder is diked, managed wetland with little to no tidal influence. There are no previously documented occurrences of soft bird's-beak in the action area. The nearest extant occurrence is approximately 4.87 miles south-southeast in Hastings Slough at the Concord Naval Weapons Station. The next nearest occurrence is approximately 5.41 miles south-southwest in the salt marshes near Martinez east of the Shell dock. (CNDDDB 2017). Based on the lack of occurrence or potential for occurrence the Service concurs with the Corps' determination that the project as described may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the soft bird's-beak. Critical habitat does not occur within the action area; therefore, none will be affected.

Suisun thistle has low potential to occur in the action area because the managed wetlands are seasonally dry and the ditches have little to no tidal influence. In the limited tidally influenced portions of the action area, the majority of the ditch banks are gently sloping, not steep. There are no previously documented occurrences of Suisun thistle in the action area. The nearest occurrences are the Rush Ranch and Joice Island population(s) approximately 7 miles northeast of the action area (CNDDDB 2017). Based on the lack of occurrence and lack of suitable habitat in the action area the Service concurs with the Corps' determination that the project as described may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the Suisun thistle.

The Corps determined that the project may affect and is likely to adversely affect the CCR and the SMHM. After review of the project description, the Service has determined the actions proposed to occur through implementation of the proposed project are likely to adversely affect the CCR, SMHM, and the delta smelt. This document hereby represents the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the CCR and the SMHM. The Service has determined that the proposed project is suitable to append to the Service's December 4, 2004, *Formal Programmatic Consultation on the Issuance of Section 10 and 404 Permits for Projects with Relatively Small Effects on Delta Smelt and its Critical Habitat* (Service File No. 1-1-04-F-0345) (Programmatic Biological Opinion) and that document represents the Service's biological opinion on the effects to the delta smelt from the proposed action.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The Goodyear Land and Development Company (GLDC) and the California Department of Water Resources (DWR) propose to construct a new Morrow Lane Bridge over Goodyear Slough to replace the existing deteriorating Morrow Lane Bridge, originally constructed in 1931 and last replaced in the early 1950s. The proposed bridge construction would occur on Morrow Lane over Goodyear Slough. The new bridge would be constructed immediately adjacent to the existing bridge. The existing bridge would remain open during construction. Upon completion of the new bridge, the old bridge would be demolished. Existing roads, pullouts on Morrow Lane on both sides of the bridge, and a GLDC storage yard at the end of Morrow Lane would be used for access, equipment staging, and material storage.

Construction of the bridge would be phased over a 2-year period. Phase 1 construction of the new bridge would require a total of 120 calendar days, with approximately 45 calendar days for in-water work. This first phase would involve removing approximately 13 wooden piles, removing vegetation, and constructing the new bridge alongside the existing bridge within the 1930's bridge alignment. Phase 2 of construction, which would involve demolishing the existing bridge, would begin during the following year no earlier than April 15, and would end no later than October 15. Demolition activities would require a total of 45 days, with approximately 20 days of in-water work. This second phase, involving the demolition and removal of the existing bridge, would be implemented during the following year. For approximately 1 year, both bridges would span Goodyear Slough. All construction work would occur Monday through Friday during daytime working hours (7 a.m. to 5 p.m.).

The proposed new one-lane bridge, approximately 16 feet wide and 208 feet long, would be constructed of steel and concrete. A minimum of 8 feet of clearance between the lowest part of the bridge bottom and the mean high-water (MHW) level of 5.42 feet North American Vertical Datum of 1988 (NAVD88) would be provided, thus placing the surface elevation of the new bridge's deck at approximately 13.42 feet above mean sea level. The new bridge would be slightly higher than the existing one. The new bridge would be constructed of concrete supported by steel girders, bents, and 36 steel piles, with each pile measuring 16 inches in diameter. An abutment that would include a 30-foot-long, 12-foot-wide concrete friction slab would be installed on both sides of Morrow Lane approaching the bridge. The 16-inch-diameter piles would be arranged in 12 columns and three rows from west to east. The piles would be driven through 50–55 feet of the slough bottom into the bedrock at a minimum of 15 feet in depth, to a total depth of approximately 65–70 feet below ground surface. The pile columns would be equally spaced 18–20 feet apart, allowing for a 20-foot-wide horizontal clearance for navigation after removal of the existing bridge. The bridge deck/driving surface would be constructed of 7-inch-thick cast-in-place concrete over 1-1/2-inch metal decking.

A galvanic cathodic protection system would be installed to protect the new bridge from corrosion. The system would consist of two anodes comprising approximately 4,000 pounds of Aloline (an alloy of aluminum and zinc, specifically formulated for use in seawater and brackish water). The cathodes would be placed on 4 feet by 10 feet steel frame sleds with a height no greater than 2 feet and installed at the mudline at the lowest points of the primary and secondary channels of Goodyear Slough. Cabling, connected to the piles, would extend from the two anodes to a test station located on the bridge's deck. An area of approximately 0.16 acre, located on both sides of Morrow Lane, would be regraded to create a smooth transition onto the bridge within the new alignment. Morrow Lane west and east of the bridge and the unnamed north-south levee road east of the bridge would remain graveled, compacted dirt. Construction activities for the new bridge would require approximately 188 cubic yards of material to be cut and approximately 144 cubic yard of fill material. The existing Morrow Lane Bridge would remain open to vehicle traffic during construction. After completion of the new bridge replacement, the existing bridge would be closed. During demolition of the existing bridge, all bridge components would be removed, including the existing bridge abutments, bridge deck, and at least 94 wooden pilings, 26 of which are encased in concrete. Minor grading and finishing along the existing roadway may be required after demolition of the existing bridge. After removal of the existing bridge, the horizontal clearance beneath the new bridge would be approximately 20 feet and sufficient for small-boat navigation.

General Construction Methods

Site Access and Staging

Access to the construction area would be provided by Goodyear Road and Morrow Lane. Construction vehicles, equipment, and building materials would be stored in staging areas at three locations near the construction site. Hazardous materials, such as petroleum and curing compounds, and waste materials would be stored in designated staging areas with proper containment and away from waterways and sensitive habitat areas.

Vegetation Removal

Minor vegetation removal would be required within the construction footprint at the eastern and western portion of the alignments where the new bridge and Morrow Lane would connect, and along the vegetated berm separating Goodyear Slough and the secondary channel. Vegetation would be removed using handheld tools in a manner intended to enable and encourage wildlife to escape from the construction area. Vegetation would be removed only with non-mechanized hand tools (trowel, hoe, rake, and shovel). No motorized equipment, including string trimmers or lawn mowers, would be used to remove vegetation. Vegetation would be removed to bare ground to the extent possible with hand tools. After the removal of vegetation, erosion and sediment controls would be installed and maintained until bridge construction commences.

Pile Removal

Old wooden piles present in the construction area would be wrapped with a choker cable or chain and removed by the "direct pull" method using the crane. Broken and damaged pilings that cannot be removed by the direct pull method would be removed by a clamshell bucket approximately 2–3 feet below the mudline. Alternatively, a diver may cut them off using a hydraulic underwater chainsaw approximately 2–3 feet below the mudline. The contractor would determine the locations of all broken and cut piles using a Global Positioning System.

Bridge Construction and Demolition

Bridge construction would initially occur from the west side of the bridge to the east side. All construction work for the proposed new bridge would occur from land using a top-down approach because the channel near the bridge is inaccessible by barge. The new bridge span would be constructed one section at a time. First, the contractor would construct the bridge abutment and install the cast-in-place concrete friction slab. Next, the first section of the bridge, comprising three piles and a bent, would be installed to allow for placement of temporary timber mats on top and the construction of the next bridge section. The timber mats would support construction equipment, including the crane and pile driving rig, as it works across the span. Timber mats are portable platforms made from hardwood timbers and are commonly used for temporary roadways, bridge decking, and equipment stabilization. Because mats would be used, construction equipment would not enter Goodyear Slough or the secondary channel. After installation of the bridge piles and bents, the deck framing would be installed in the reverse direction (east to west) and the concrete drive surface would be poured. Concrete curing procedures involving water or chemical applications may be necessary depending on weather conditions. During construction and demolition activities, debris-catching devices such as netting and covers would be used to protect water bodies from debris and wastes associated with construction in Goodyear Slough. Debris-catching devices would be emptied regularly, and collected debris would be removed and stored away from waterways and protected from run-on and runoff. Booms would also be placed in Goodyear Slough upstream and downstream of the bridge to capture and immediately remove any debris or construction material that may fall into the water.

Materials and Waste Management

Material for construction of the proposed new bridge would be obtained from construction providers in Antioch, approximately 25 miles from the project area. The contractor estimates that approximately 11 truck trips would be required to obtain bridge materials and approximately 17 truck deliveries of concrete. Removal of existing piles in the new bridge alignment and the demolition of the existing bridge would result in approximately 250 cubic yards of waste material comprising treated and non-treated wood, concrete, and metal. Non-hazardous waste would be hauled and disposed of at the Contra Costa Transfer and Recovery Station in Martinez, approximately 10 miles south of the project area. Treated wood waste and hazardous materials, such as petroleum, would be stored in the designated staging areas. Treated wood wastes, consisting of 94 or more piles, concrete, and bridge decking, would be stored, handled, and disposed of in accordance with applicable regulations at an appropriate licensed Class 1 or composite-lined portion of a solid waste landfill, such as Potrero Hills Landfill in Suisun City, approximately 20 miles northeast of the project area.

Conservation Measures

General

- Prepare and implement an erosion and sediment control plan. An erosion and sediment control plan will be prepared by GLDC, DWR and/or construction contractors before ground-disturbing construction begins. The plan will include site-specific erosion-control, sedimentation-control, and runoff measures that will be implemented during construction to minimize the potential for bridge construction and demolition to cause erosion and sedimentation. As applicable, tightly woven fiber netting (mesh size less than 0.25 inch) or similar material will be used for erosion control and other purposes in the construction and staging areas to ensure that wildlife do not become trapped or entangled in the erosion control material. Coconut coir (fiber) matting is an acceptable material for erosion control, but no plastic monofilament matting will be used for erosion control.
- Prepare and implement a spill prevention and control program. A spill prevention and control program will be prepared by GLDC, DWR and/or construction contractors before the start of construction to minimize the potential for hazardous, toxic, or petroleum substances to be released in areas of construction. The program will be implemented during construction. In addition, sandbags, biologs, or other containment features will be placed around areas used for fueling or other hazardous materials that may be used, to prevent these materials from accidentally leaking into nearby wetlands and sloughs. Construction activities will adhere to standard construction best management practices (BMPs) described in the current version of the California Department of Transportation (Caltrans) Construction Site Best Management Practices Manual.
- Prepare and implement a hazardous materials and waste management program. A hazardous materials and waste management program will be prepared and implemented by GLDC, DWR and/or construction contractors in accordance with existing regulations to identify the hazardous materials to be used during construction; describe measures to prevent, control, and minimize the spillage of hazardous substances; and describe transport, storage, and disposal procedures for these substances and other waste materials

generated during construction and demolition activities. The program will require that hazardous or potentially hazardous substances stored on-site be kept in securely closed containers located away from drainage courses, storm drains, and areas where stormwater is allowed to infiltrate. It will also stipulate procedures to minimize hazards during on-site fueling and servicing of construction equipment. The program will also include BMPs and health and safety procedures for cutting, removing, storing, handling, and transporting treated wood and treated wood waste (i.e., removed piles) in accordance with California Health and Safety Code Section 25143.15 and other applicable regulations. All employees removing piles will be qualified and properly trained on hazards and handling procedures, and will be provided with the appropriate level of personal protective equipment necessary for the work performed. Treated wood waste (removed piles) will be stored in a leak-proof containment basin that will be constructed to contain all sediment, water, and pile debris and allow for easy waste separation. The treated wood waste will then be cut to size and sediment will be containerized for disposal and scheduled for transport to an appropriate licensed Class 1 or composite-lined portion of a solid waste landfill. If needed, waste material will be tested before being transported off-site. Construction and demolition activities will adhere to standard Best Management Practices (BMPs) related to hazardous materials and waste management described in the current Caltrans Construction Site Best Management Practices Manual.

- Minimize disturbance during construction. To the extent possible, construction and staging areas will be limited to the existing right-of-way and previously disturbed areas. The boundaries of construction areas will be clearly demarcated by construction contractors. Any new disturbance, including grading, will occur in the smallest area necessary.
- Minimize wildlife attraction. To eliminate attraction of wildlife to the action area, all food related trash items, such as wrappers, cans, bottles, and food scraps, will be disposed of in closed containers and removed from the project site by construction contractors on a daily basis.
- Implement a Worker Environmental Awareness Program. Construction workers will participate in a worker environmental awareness program that addresses species under the jurisdiction of the Service. Workers will be informed about the potential presence of listed species and their habitats. Before construction activities begin, a qualified biologist will instruct all construction workers about the terms and conditions of the regulatory permits that include biological resource protection measures. A copy of the permitting documents will be kept on-site at all times.
- Conduct biological monitoring. A qualified biologist will be on-site daily during mobilization and vegetation removal, fencing installation, all ground disturbing activities, and to monitor in-water construction activities. Outside of the aforementioned construction activities, the biologist will conduct periodic compliance inspections. The biologist will keep a copy of the permitting documents in his/her possession when on-site. The biologist will document compliance with the proposed project's permit conditions and avoidance and conservation measures. The biologist will have the authority to stop activities for the proposed project if any of the requirements associated

with permit measures are not being fulfilled. If the biologist exercises this authority, the permitting agencies will be notified within 1 working day via e-mail or telephone.

California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse

- Restrict construction timing to protect CCR and SMHM. Construction activity occurring between September 1 and January 31 will be conducted only when high tides are not at their winter extremes to reduce the likelihood that CCR and/or SMHM will be present in the construction areas. Construction next to the marsh will be avoided during the highest tides of December and January (approximately 1 week each month).
- Remove vegetation outside CCR breeding season. Any vegetation removal required for bridge construction will be conducted between September 1 and February 1, outside of the CCR breeding season. To avoid impacts on CCR and SMHM, a pre-disturbance survey will be conducted by a qualified biologist immediately before the start of any vegetation removal activities. Vegetation will be removed only under the close supervision of the biologist approved by the Service. If a mouse or rail of any species is observed in the areas where vegetation is being removed, the Service will be notified. Vegetation removal will start at the edge farthest from the salt marsh or the poorest habitat and work its way toward the salt marsh or the better salt marsh habitat during periods when no mice or rails are observed. Vegetation will be removed only with non-mechanized hand tools (trowel, hoe, rake, and shovel). No motorized equipment, including string trimmers or lawn mowers, will be used to remove this vegetation. Vegetation will be removed to bare ground.
- Install temporary exclusion fencing (TEF). After vegetation removal and prior to the start of construction activities, TEF will be installed under the direction of a biologist and will be adequate to exclude CCR and SMHM from construction areas. The TEF should be made of a heavy plastic sheeting material that does not allow SMHM to pass through or climb over. The bottom of the sheeting should be buried to a depth of 2 inches so that these species cannot crawl under the fence. All fencing support will be placed in the interior of the action area. The TEF will be at least 12 inches higher than the highest adjacent vegetation up to a maximum height of 4 feet. TEF will be removed after all construction and demolition is complete. Before the start of daily construction activities, the qualified biological monitor will inspect the TEF to ensure that it is rip-free and has no holes, and that the base is still buried. The fenced area will also be inspected to ensure that no mice are trapped in it. Any mice found along and outside the fence will be closely monitored until they move away from the construction area. Any materials or supplies that could potentially entrap SMHM will be checked for the presence of mice and other wildlife before movement or use. All equipment will be stored at the GLDC storage yards, in designated staging areas, or along access roads when not in use.
- Conduct pre-construction surveys for CCR and SMHM. To ensure that CCR and SMHM nest sites are not disturbed by construction from February through July, a qualified biologist will conduct preconstruction surveys. If active nests of either species are found during the surveys, the Service will be consulted regarding adequate avoidance measures. A biologist will determine the extent of a fenced construction-free buffer zone to be established around the nest in consultation with the Service. Intensive new disturbances

(e.g., heavy-equipment activities associated with construction) that may cause nest abandonment, a reduction in the level of care provided by adults (e.g., duration of brooding, frequency of feeding), or forced fledging will not begin within this buffer zone until the biologist has determined, in coordination with the Service, that the young have fledged and are feeding on their own.

- **Conduct Biological Monitoring.** The Service-approved biological monitor will be on call during construction to respond and assist the construction crew with environmental issues as necessary. If a CCR or SMHM, or any mouse or rail that construction personnel believe to be these species is encountered during construction, all construction activities will cease and the foreman and the biologist will be immediately notified. Work will remain stopped until the individual(s) moves out of the work area unassisted, appropriate corrective measures have been completed, or it has been determined that the species will not be harmed. The biologist will monitor individual mice or rails until he or she determines that the animal(s) will not be imperiled. The biologist will notify the Service via e-mail and telephone within 1 working day after any encounters with a potential CCR or SMHM during construction. Information reported will include date(s), location(s), habitat description, and any collective measures taken to protect the species.
- **Minimize Noise Generation to Avoid Disturbing Special-Status Wildlife.** Noise will be minimized to the extent feasible in the Action Area to avoid disturbing CCR or SMHM.
- **GLDC will provide compensatory mitigation for potential loss of northern coastal salt marsh habitat by contributing \$20,000 to CDFW (via Ducks Unlimited) for on-the-ground restoration activities at the Hill Slough Restoration Project Site.**

Delta smelt¹

- **Observe the National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) in-water work window.** In-water work will be restricted to periods between June 15 and September 30, unless otherwise specified by NMFS, the Service, and/or other appropriate regulatory agencies.
- **Manage debris.** Debris generated during construction activities will be properly managed to avoid adverse impacts to water quality and aquatic environments. Booms and other debris-catching devices, such as netting and covers, will be used by construction contractors to protect water bodies from debris and wastes associated with structure demolition or removal over or adjacent to Goodyear Slough. Debris-catching devices will also be emptied by construction contractors regularly and collected debris will be removed and stored away from waterways and protected from run-on and runoff.
- **Implement pile removal BMPs.** A vibration removal method will not be used to avoid splintering, crumbling and/or otherwise disintegrating the piles due to their age and existing condition. The removed piles will be temporarily stored on-site within a

¹ Although the conservation measures were proposed for listed fish under jurisdiction of NMFS, the Service has recognized that the measures proposed are appropriate for protection of the delta smelt.

containment area and transported back to the contractor's staging area where the concrete will be separated from the other materials and recycled or disposed of off-site, as appropriate, at a permitted facility. The containment area will be designed in such a way as to prohibit sediment or debris from falling back into the water. The work areas will include a containment basin for piles, concrete, and any mud or sediment removed during pulling. Upon removal from substrate, the piles will be moved expeditiously from the water into the containment area. When the removal method selected is expected to generate concrete chips or dust in the water, a special curtain will be deployed around the individual pile so the contractor may capture any concrete pieces for off-site disposal. Intentional breaking of timber piles above the mudline is prohibited. The piles will not be shaken, hosed off, stripped, or scraped off, left hanging to drip, nor will any other action be taken with the intent of cleaning or removing adhering material from the pile. Any sediment accumulated from the pile removal operations will be assumed to contain creosote and will be contained and disposed off-site in an appropriate landfill. Identified broken and damaged piling stubs will be cut off at 2–3 feet below the mudline, if possible. Holes remaining after pile removal will be left to fill in through natural sediment settlement and deposition.

- Conduct underwater sound monitoring. Underwater sound monitoring will be conducted by a qualified acoustics expert during all pile-driving and pile removal activities. Underwater sound levels will not exceed peak-pressure, accumulated sound-exposure-level (SEL), or root-mean-square (RMS) thresholds, as determined using NMFS requirements for the proposed project. To the maximum extent possible, underwater sound readings will be collected downstream at a distance determined using NMFS calculations for pile-driving activities and may be adjusted based on site conditions and safety considerations. The monitoring distance is estimated to be 5–10 meters (approximately 16.4 to 32.8 feet) from each pile, depending on the equipment set up on-site each day for each pile, and may vary up to 20 meters (approximately 65.6 feet) from each pile. The impact distance will be determined for fish species with the potential to occur in the action area using NMFS requirements for the project. The impact distance is estimated to be 3 to 13 feet from each pile.
- Employ noise attenuation measures. If sound thresholds established by NMFS are exceeded, construction activities will be temporarily halted. Alternatively, construction contractors may employ sound-deadening cushions, pile encasings, or air bubble curtains around piles. Pile-driving activities may also be limited for short time periods during daylight hours.
- Implement a soft-start pile-driving technique. The contractor will implement a soft-start technique for impact pile-driving. A soft-start technique is an initial set of strikes at reduced energy followed by a 30-second waiting period; this procedure is then repeated two additional times before continuous pile-driving begins. This technique will be used before pile-driving begins each day and any time after pile-driving ceases for 30 minutes or longer.
- Monitor water quality. Water quality monitoring for turbidity, dissolved oxygen, pH, and water temperature will be conducted by GLDC, DWR and/or its construction contractors upstream and downstream of construction work during pile-driving and pile removal

activities to ensure that the proposed project complies with mandated thresholds for meeting water quality objectives. Visual observations for turbidity plumes, sheens, or black-colored water will also be performed. If water quality thresholds are exceeded, in-channel water control measures will be implemented.

- Deploy in-channel water quality controls. If water quality thresholds could be exceeded, pile-driving and pile removal activities may be limited for short time periods or work may be temporarily halted until ambient water quality conditions return to concentrations below threshold levels. Alternatively, appropriate turbidity and siltation control measures will be deployed by construction contractors to reduce effects. These measures may include a turbidity barrier, curtain, or diffusion mat. The appropriate controls will be rated according to wind speed, wave height, and the flow velocity of Goodyear Slough. Installing a turbidity barrier would have the added benefit of excluding fish from the immediate area of in-water work (i.e., pile-driving and pile removal).

Action Area

The action area is defined as all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action (50 CFR 402.02). The action area for this section 7 consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the project and the broader area that, while outside the construction zone, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, dust, or movement associated with the proposed project. The action area includes the project footprint and staging and access areas. After review of the BA and the project description, the Service determines that the action area includes the existing bridge, the waters immediately adjacent to the Morrow Lane Bridge, the GLDC storage yard, two roadside staging areas, and existing paved, gravel, and dirt roads that provide vehicular access between these areas. The action area totals approximately 95 acres and encompasses the entire 0.62-acre construction footprint, the staging areas, and a 700-foot buffer for noise disturbance in the salt marsh on either side of the Morrow Lane. This distance was determined by the Service based on telemetry studies (Albertson 1995) that estimated the average area of a CCR home range equivalent to a circle with a 450-foot radius; the Service then added a 250-foot buffer zone to that distance to ensure avoidance, to arrive at 700 feet.

Status of Species

California Clapper Rail

The status of California clapper rail and information about its biology, ecology, distribution, and current threats is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Service 2013). This document can be found at:

https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf.

Critical habitat has not been designated for this species.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*). Both subspecies are listed as endangered. The status of the salt marsh harvest mouse and information about its biology,

ecology, distribution, and current threats is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Service 2013). This document can be found at: https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf. Critical habitat has not been designated for this species.

Delta Smelt

The status of the species has been updated since the issuance of the Programmatic Biological Opinion. Please refer to page 6 of the 2010 delta smelt 5 year review and page 70151 of the 2013 Candidate Notice of Review for the status of the species. Electronic copies of these documents are available at http://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc3570.pdf and <http://www.gpo.gov/fdsys/pkg/FR-2013-11-22/pdf/2013-27391.pdf>.

Currently, the spawning stock of delta smelt appears to be at its second lowest abundance on record, the lowest having been recorded during Water Year 2016 (Table 1). The 2017 Fall Midwater Trawl (FMWT) Index was 8, the second lowest value on record. The CDFW Spring Kodiak Trawl (SKT) monitors the adult spawning stock of delta smelt and serves as an indication for the relative number and distribution of spawners in the system. The Service has calculated an absolute abundance estimate for adult spawners in water year 2017 using January and February SKT data. This absolute abundance estimate² is also the second lowest on record (Table 1). The population size of adult delta smelt January-February (2017) was estimated to be between 22,000 and 92,000 fish with a point estimate of 47,786. The January-February (2016) point estimates were the lowest values since 2002 and suggested delta smelt experienced increased mortality during extreme drought conditions occurring during 2013-2015. While 2017 estimates likely represent an increase in recruitment and survival from the prior year, the continued low parental stock of delta smelt relative to historical numbers suggest the population will continue to be vulnerable to stochastic events and operational changes that may occur in response until successive years of increased population growth result in a substantial increase of abundance.

Table 1.

Three indicators of adult delta smelt status for water years 2002-2017. Column 2 is the CDFW Fall Midwater Trawl Index by water year (i.e., the indices for calendar years 2001-2017). Column 3 is the CDFW Spring Kodiak Trawl Index. Column 4 is an estimate of adult delta smelt abundance during January and February that the Service calculates from the Spring Kodiak Trawl Survey.

<u>Water Year</u>	<u>FMWT Index (unitless)</u>	<u>SKT Index (unitless)</u>	<u>Jan-Feb SKT abundance estimate (thousands of fish)</u>
2002	603	N/A	739.8
2003	139	N/A	634
2004	210	99.7	654.5
2005	74	52.9	477.8
2006	26	18.2	186.8

² The Service completed a new adult delta smelt abundance estimation procedure based on CDFW's SKT data for January and February (see Table 1). This procedure has recently been updated from that used in 2016. While these estimates likely represent a minimum population size due to the method's reliance on survey data, this is our current best estimate of population size.

2007	41	32.5	292
2008	28	24.1	325.3
2009	23	43.8	365.9
2010	17	27.4	169.4
2011	29	18.8	290.8
2012	343	130.2	772.3
2013	42	20.4	212.5
2014	18	30.1	207.6
2015	9	13.8	139.3
2016	7	1.8	16.2
2017	8	3.8	47.8

Environmental Baseline

The proposed project is located on the west edge of Suisun Bay in the southwest tip of the Suisun Marsh.

Eight occurrences of salt marsh harvest mouse have been documented within 3 miles of the action area (CNDDDB 2017). The closest occurrence is immediately east of the action area, approximately 0.2 mile east of the Ehmann Duck Club (a facility adjacent to the GLDC storage yard). The next two nearest occurrences are approximately 1.0 mile to the north and 1.1 miles to the south. Suitable habitat is present and salt marsh harvest mouse could potentially occur in the action area.

California clapper rail occurs sporadically and in low numbers at various locations throughout the Suisun Marsh area. They have been found recurrently since 1978 in marshes near the mouth of Goodyear Slough and in shoreline marshes from Martinez east to Port Chicago, Suisun and Hill sloughs, and the western reaches of Cutoff Slough (Herzog *et al.* 2005; Service 2013). There are six occurrences within 3 miles of the action area (CNDDDB 2017). The closest occurrence is approximately 0.58 mile to the southeast in managed marsh. The next closest occurrences are 1.24 miles northeast on Morrow Island just west of the mouth of Suisun Slough, and approximately 1.77 miles south at the south end of Goodyear Slough. Suitable habitat is present and CCR could potentially occur in the action area.

Continued monitoring for several decades by the University of California, Davis in Goodyear Slough has shown that the presence of delta smelt in the action area is very rare. A total of seven delta smelt were captured between 1979 and 2015 (Moyle 2016). However, precipitation to date during Water Year 2017 has been recorded as the wettest on record in the Sacramento Valley Basin and resulting high outflows from the Sacramento-San Joaquin River Delta have caused spawning delta smelt to be pushed out towards the Bay, as evidenced by data collected by CDFW and the Service during regular fish monitoring surveys. Delta smelt have been recorded in the Carquinez Strait, east San Pablo Bay, and the lower Napa River. As a result, the progeny of this year's spawning stock may occur in the vicinity of the project area where they will rear until the subsequent winter migration. This is especially likely if the low-salinity zone remains near Carquinez Strait. Goodyear Slough is a tidally influenced waterway that connects to Suisun Slough which then feeds directly into Grizzly Bay. Delta smelt are known to occur within the

waterways of the Suisun Marsh Complex and Goodyear Slough could provide suitable habitat for delta smelt during this current water year and similar water years in the future.

Effects of the Proposed Project

California Clapper Rail

Noise, vibrations, and visual disturbance from construction activities and heavy equipment may result in the harassment of individual CCR in the adjacent habitat and expose them to predation if they were flushed from cover or prevented from seeking available cover. Noise or other construction disturbance during the CCR breeding season (February 1-August 31) could result in the loss of breeding activity or nest abandonment and the loss of all eggs and chicks in the nest. To minimize adverse effects to breeding, work is planned to occur outside of the nesting season (September 1 – January 31). Vegetation removal and grading activities for construction of the new bridge alignment approach have the potential to result in permanent direct impacts through loss of habitat. Permanent impacts would amount to the loss of approximately 0.08 acre of northern coastal salt marsh habitat that consists of approximately 0.04 acre of permanent loss with the placement of bridge components and 0.04 acre due to shading from the bridge deck.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The proposed project could cause displacement of SMHM if individuals were compelled to move away from construction and demolition activities to avoid being disturbed. Displaced individuals could be exposed to increased risk from predation, competition, and reduced reproductive success through abandonment of a nesting area, failure to breed, or abandonment or failure of a litter. Potential displacement of SMHM individuals would be minimized through the use of preconstruction surveys and monitoring by a Service- approved biologist during hand removal of vegetation and installation of exclusion fencing. Wetlands in the action area could become contaminated during construction if fuel or other hazardous materials were to spill into the channel or adjacent wetlands. Contamination of wetlands or waters would be minimized by implementing a spill prevention plan, BMPs, and a storm water pollution prevention plan. Vegetation removal and grading activities for construction of the new bridge alignment approach have the potential to result in permanent direct impacts through loss of habitat. Impacts would amount to approximately 0.08 acre of northern coastal salt marsh habitat that consists of approximately 0.04 acre of permanent loss with the placement of bridge components and 0.04 acre due to shading from the bridge deck.

Delta Smelt

The Programmatic Biological Opinion has project work windows beginning on August 1 and ending November 30. The applicant however has proposed a work window from June 15 through September 30 for protection of listed fish under jurisdiction of NMFS. The Service has reviewed the status of the species within the action area and determined that due to the near absence of delta smelt observed in Goodyear Slough through several years of continued monitoring, that the proposed project is not expected to result in any additional effects not already analyzed in the Programmatic Biological Opinion. The temporary effects resulting from construction of the new bridge and demolition of the old bridge will be reduced by conducting the proposed project

during periods between June 15 and September 30 and incorporation of conservation measures, which are consistent with the guidelines of the Programmatic Biological Opinion.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. The Service is not aware of specific projects that might affect the CCR, SMHM or delta smelt in the action area that are currently under review by State, county, or local authorities.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of the CCR, SMHM, delta smelt, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed action, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the CCR, SMHM or delta smelt. This is based on the small size of the affected suitable habitat area, the fact that habitat disturbance will be temporary and short-term, and the implementation of conservation measures.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by the Service as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to a listed species by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavioral patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding or sheltering. Harm is defined by the Service to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act, provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicants, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicants to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of individual CCR, SMHM and delta smelt will be difficult to detect or quantify because of the variable, unknown size of any resident population over time, their elusive and cryptic behavior, and the difficulty of finding killed or injured animals. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of CCR, SMHM and delta smelt that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the Service is quantifying take incidental to the proposed project as the following:

1. Harassment of all CCR and SMHM within suitable habitat of the action area (approximately 95 acres and encompasses the entire 0.62-acre construction footprint, staging areas, and a 700-foot buffer for noise disturbance in the salt marsh on either side of the Morrow Lane.).
2. Harassment of all delta smelt within suitable aquatic habitat of the action area (approximately 2 acres within the Goodyear Slough channel).

Upon implementation of the reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determines that the levels of take are not likely to result in jeopardy to the CCR, SMHM or the delta smelt.

Reasonable and Prudent Measures

The following reasonable and prudent measures are necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the proposed project to the CCR, SMHM and the delta smelt:

1. The Corps will minimize the potential for harassment of CCR, SMHM and delta smelt.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure that the applicants comply with the following terms and conditions, which implement their respective reasonable and prudent measures described above. These terms and conditions are non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. The Corps shall minimize the potential for harm, harassment, injury, killing or other forms of take of the CCR, SMHM and delta smelt from project related activities by implementation of the Conservation Measures as described in the Project Description in this biological opinion or as modified by the Terms and Conditions of this document.

- b. The Corps shall ensure that the applicants immediately notify the Service of any killed, injured, or entrapped CCR, SMHM, or delta smelt, within one (1) working day of the detection. Please contact the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-5603.
- c. The Corps shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the Conservation Measures and Terms and Conditions in this biological opinion.
- d. The Corps shall comply with the reporting requirements of this biological opinion, including a post-construction report outlining how the Conservation Measures were implemented for this project.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, the Corps shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. Injured listed species shall be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed project. Notification will be made to the contact above in Term and Condition 1b, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the Disposition of Individuals Taken section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and California Natural Diversity Database (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/CNDDDB/Submitting-Data>).
3. The applicants shall submit a post-construction compliance report prepared by the on-site biologist to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within sixty (60) calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the project in meeting the avoidance and minimization measures; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known project effects on the CCR, SMHM, and delta smelt if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take of these listed species, if any; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information.

Disposition of Individuals Taken

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact persons are the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-5603; and the Resident Agent-in-Charge of the Service's Office of Law Enforcement, 5622 Price Way, McClellan, California 95562, at (916) 569-8444.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

1. Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in re-vegetation efforts.
2. Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.
3. Assist the Service in implementing other recovery actions identified within most current recovery plans for the CCR, SMHM and delta smelt.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation for the Goodyear Slough Morrow Lane Bridge Replacement Project. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16, reinitiation of formal consultation is required where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained (or is authorized by law) and if: (1) the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded; (2) new information reveals effects of the agency action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not considered in this opinion; (3) the agency action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat not considered in this opinion; or (4) a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the action. In instances where the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded, any additional take will not be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, pending reinitiation.

If you have any questions regarding this response to the Goodyear Slough Morrow Lane Bridge Replacement Project, please contact Brian Hansen, Fish and Wildlife Biologist, at Brian_Hansen@fws.gov or by telephone at (916) 930-5642 or Kim Squires, Section 7 Coordinator, via email at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 08FBDT00-2017-F-0045 in any future correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Kaylee Allen', written in a cursive style.

for Kaylee Allen
Field Supervisor

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